

MOTIVATIONS AND AN ATHLETE'S LONG-TERM COMMITMENT TO A SPORT

by

Ava Parson

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Approved by:

Date:

Melinda Blackman

5/17/24

Dr. Melinda Blackman, Department of Psychology

5/24/24

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University
Honors Program

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ABSTRACT

Talent, dedication, or motivation: What determines how long an athlete pursues their sport? The individual's journey pursuing the game is marked by various motivations. These motivations can be categorized as intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic motivations are stirred by a sense of inherent fulfillment, regardless of any external factors. Conversely, extrinsic motivations are the factors that exist outside of the person that spur them to be motivated. This case study took an individualized approach to explore these different types of motivations within athletes as they relate to their time as an athlete and their long-term commitment to the sport. Four collegiate athletes from different sports were interviewed to gain qualitative and quantitative data insight. The analysis process reviewed the data individually, across cases, and with pre-existing research and theories surrounding the subject matter. Results for all four athletes' quantitative data showed higher intrinsic motivation in their relation to their sport, compared to extrinsic motivation. Alongside the self-determination theory, relatedness and autonomy were found in multiple areas of the athlete's journey and mindset, and further validated in the importance of the relationship with their team in ordinal data. These are all positive. Overarching commonalities include the weight of a winning game, the role of professional athletes in inspiration, the diversification of sports played, and the mindsets that are a part of the full length of the athlete's journey. With three of the four athletes planning to go professional, the long-term commitment these athletes have shown and prepare to step into in the future are optimistically backed by overcoming the barriers that usually lead to drop out rates among athletes found in different studies. The application of these findings can aid in understanding how to go about facilitating the growth of a team sports athlete, with the individual in mind, which sustains the enthusiasm and dedication of an athlete. This study may also inform college coaches. Additionally, to give

insight to athletic companies so they can supply athletes with effective goods and services that work in tandem with their driving motivations.

INTRODUCTION

Within team sports, there are a range of factors that can determine how an athlete performs in each game. Motivation, in its different applications, has a high propensity to further predict the way that an athlete will perform. While the research of motivation pertaining to athlete performance is valuable, going further than just measuring the extent of success or failure is opening the door to valuable application. Exploring how various intrinsic and extrinsic motivations affect the length of an athlete's participation in a team sport can provide additional insight to aid in understanding an athlete's journey within their sport. Comprehending the motivations which sustain the interest and participation of an athlete is gaining knowledge on how we, as a society, can better support and be aware of their journey in team sports. The implications of this research could range anywhere from building awareness for coaches and peers, to aiding in marketing strategies to supply athletes with proper goods and services that tailor to their wants and needs. A preliminary literature review explores the present and past research in the subject matter, as well as gaps in the research or sample population that could provide an avenue for this research. Specifically, the lack of U.S athletes beyond adolescence did not have much research for this subject matter. Also, it compares the different trends in varying motivations between athletes based on various factors. These factors would include level of team sport, type of team sport, and gender. Relevant sport psychology material pertaining to this research is also explored and elaborated on.

PRE-EXISTING STUDIES

The Motivations of Athletes

A variety of research has already been a part of this conversation, as analysis on different endurance sports and team sports have been reviewed through different test cases involving athletes from different regions. The research often focuses on the use of the Sport Motivation scale, or some alteration of it, to drive the framework of survey style for the specific test group. Also, there is often an established psychological theory used along with the Sport Motivation scale to lay the foundation of the hypothesis or problem statement. An example of this would include the use of the self-determination theory, to build conclusions and compare them between male and female college athletes. This was the approach that Rajmund Tomik and Magdalena Ardenska used in a Polish study that examined student athletes' motivation toward sport participation with an emphasis on the comparison between male and female University student athletes (Tomik et al.,2020). Their findings concluded that among the higher ratio of male to female participants, that female participants reacted more towards intrinsic motivations than males did (Tomik et al., 2020). Further, existing research in this field of interest does not always compare diverse types of sports or include gender as a factor in the research.

However, a common trend that does exist, in a variety of studies, is the inclusion of a self-made survey to focus testing an additional variable alongside motivation. Using additional means of questioning alongside a standard scale for surveying is what Michaela Cocca, Armando Cocca, Ney Augusto Da Silva, and Luis Tomas Rodenas Cuenca did when conducting their research. They created a survey themselves to investigate the impact of music with motivation and flow state for athletes competing in the 2017 University Olympics of Mexico (Cocca et al., 2018). The survey consisted of a questionnaire created specifically for this study, as well as the Sport

Motivation Scale and the Flow State Scale (Cocca et al., 2018). The findings were optimistic towards concluding that there are positive relations between music and an athletes' psychological wellbeing surrounding their performance in competitions and training. A potential weakness of this study's conclusions section was that it did not include any differentiation in the data as it pertained to male or female, or any other criteria to characterize or compare the sample.

Passion was another variable that was used in looking at motivation and effort with athletes through a lens of looking at psychological needs, autonomous motivation, and overall effort (Yukhymenko-Lescroart 2021). This article, by Mariya A. Yukhymenko-Lescroart, looked not only at athletic performance, but academic as well. For the purpose of this particular research topic, it is interesting to look at how harmonious passion for sport was indicative of positive sport competence, as found in the results portion of the journal article (Yukhymenko-Lescroart 2021). This study gives strong insight into the comparative nature between the strengths and weaknesses of harmonious passion and obsessive passion for a sport. As my research aims to distinguish positive and healthy motivations from motivations that lead to burnout or unhealthy habits, this information provides constructive commentary and findings on that topic.

Another study that is beneficial to look at, both in methodology and in resounding conclusions, was with research pertaining to basketball athletes. Lithuanian regional basketball teams of a wide range of ages, 18-34, were tested to find if emotional intelligence was a useful tool in predicting their motivation to participate in sports (Sukys et al., 2019). This study used a modified Sport Motivation Scale in conjunction with the 1998 developed EI scale to find the relationship between them, to motivation (Sukys et al., 2019). One of the fascinating findings of this study was the claim made that an athlete's ability to regulate emotion correlated to their

interest and participation, as lack of control over emotions related to lack of interest (Sukys et al., 2019). A strength of this study was that it was inclusive of a variety of ages, so that there was a wider understanding of the sample's trends and patterns being applicable beyond the specified sample. The disadvantage to this sample size however, was that there was only one team sport in one region that was highlighted for this study. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from this data may better be suited to suggest those of just basketball players, because it may not apply to other areas if no other athlete other than a basketball player was a part of this sample. Once again, an analysis that produces clarified indications of positive and negative effects on motivation through varied factors, such as emotional intelligence, music, or passion, are all furthering the ways that how motivation is prompted, does matter.

The Longevity of an Athlete's Career

Research done by Windee M. Weiss, Maureen R. Weiss, and Anthony J. Amorose built upon prior studies' research on attraction-based commitment and entrapment-based commitment. They did this through looking at a perspective of studying perceived costs, regarding other theoretical predictors (Weiss et al., 2010). In doing so, they focused on their sample of female gymnasts. A potential weakness, that the authors acknowledge in their testing limitations, was the confusion that may have occurred between the question format that addressed enjoyment and involvement opportunities as being alike, when there is an intended difference between the way that they are meant to be perceived. However, I do not think that negated any of their work's contribution and validity to the methodology they had referenced earlier in their work. That is, because their conclusions were well founded through the results of their data, and even went further to test variables that had scarcely been explored. Another study sought to analyze the motivations that

led to a female athlete's long-term commitment to the sport at various levels, regarding both independent and collective variables that they outlined in their work (Domínguez-Escribano et al., 2017). The strength of this study was the use of a cross analysis between levels of female soccer players, so that there could be comparison between the growth that can occur in the motivational development between ages and levels of players (Domínguez-Escribano et al., 2017). An interesting correlation was found that it was not the level of the sport that influenced the commitment to the sport, but the age did, as the younger women showed more commitment than those older than them (Domínguez-Escribano et al., 2017).

Sport Psychology's Integration with the Subject Matter

The sources used to build a foundation of understanding for the sport psychology pertaining to this topic, included the commentary from Kent Berridge in relating emotion to motivation. Kent Berridge highlights the evolution in motivation theories within psychology by reviewing drive and drive reduction theories with incentive motivation theories (Berridge 2018). Specifically, how the environment has moved away from motivation correlating strongly to negative drive theories, but positive incentive theories of motivation (Berridge 2018). This is relevant for the research on this topic because having a fundamental understanding of the psychology within motivation is pertinent to creating a framework that connects where athletes' motivations come from. Specifically, the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and how it affects their performance and commitment to the sport. Simply defined, intrinsic motivation is the motivations stirred by the internal, and inherent, fulfillment it gives, regardless of external factors (Reiss 2012). On the other hand, extrinsic motivations are the factors that exist outside of the person that spur them forward to be motivated considering that exterior factor (Reiss 2012). The two can relate in a

variety of ways, as Reiss quotes, “According to Deci and Ryan’s (1985) self-determination theory, extrinsic incentives undermine intrinsic interest” (Reiss 2012). Also, looking at the Flow State Scale, with the Sports Motivation Scale, can be beneficial for drawing conclusions based on multiple accredited scales of measurement. The Sport Motivation Scale is a questionnaire that breaks down the motivations of its participant into three categories, intrinsic extrinsic and amotivated motivations, based on the question (Mallett et al., 2007). The use of team sports, compared to athletes participating in individual sports, makes a difference in how the athlete interacts with the sport and their contribution to it. This is summarized well through the quote, “In contrast to individual sports, team sports athletes are involved with teammates and spend time training together and interacting often with each other (Kajbafnezhad et al., 2011), which also allows the pressure felt by athletes during the training sessions and competitions to be shared between members of a team” (Sukys et al., 2019). Therefore, the motivations that may exist within an athlete are likely to have differences than if they were competing solely on behalf of themselves. Additionally, self-determination theory’s role in this research would align well with the topic because it relates closely to intrinsic motivation. Specifically, in taking a critical analysis of the role of relatedness, autonomy, and competence in the touchpoints of these athlete’s lives. The self-determination theory is a general theory of human motivation that relates to the development of the personality regarding social contexts and numerous factors (Ryan et al., 2017). It plays a unique and crucial role in the context of an athlete, due to the motivations that extend beyond our personal psychological needs, into the needs that encompass the goals of the game.

In conclusion, the research, commentary, and overall contributions from these sources aid in this research topic’s development. These resources also hold value in that there will be potential for

determining if there are any connections between the results of this research, and the results of the former studies listed. Through the discussion of the different subtopics regarding the sources, the takeaways from each are unique to their purpose, in engaging with answering the questions of the motivations that contribute to an athlete's overall performance and longevity of participation in the sport.

RESEARCH AIMS

The focus of the study will be looking into the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations that correlate to an athlete's performance and long-term commitment to their sport. This will be measured and interpreted through collecting data from athletes that are a part of a team sport, at the collegiate level. One aim of this study is to connect if there are any leading intrinsic and extrinsic motivations that exist across team sport athletes and if there are any commonalities between the several types of sports. Additionally, to answer the questions, are these motivations perpetuating positive or negative long-term effects, and are there any commonalities between the athletes' prominent needs based on the self-determination theory? For example, do they come from states of fear or passion, or a feeling of responsibility? Or are factors such as academics, physical health, social status, or family connections behind the wheel for driving the avenues of motivations pertaining to the athlete. These questions also can contribute to the analysis for relations between what drives or deters an athlete from their commitment to the sport they participate in. To answer these questions, the control factors of the level of team sport, type of team sport, and gender were a part of the recruitment process. These players' statistics, or otherwise rank of their ability, by any game play metrics, were not included in the process. Details such as the length of time they have spent with their sport, or what other sports teams they had been a part of were not clarified or considered before the research. This was to maintain

the integrity of their long-term commitment to the sport before investigation. Finally, a descriptive case study format was taken because the case study aims to find the connection between the subject studied, in this case the college athlete, and the theories surrounding external and internal motivation. Therefore, representative of this case study's size, the results align with how to develop the theories and research questions in future studies.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this research is to provide reputable insight into connecting college athletes' motivations to their performance and the longevity of their participation in the sport that can benefit the understanding of how these athletes operate on a psychological level. The steps involving this study can be separated into two distinct phases. That is, the steps that pertain to the preparation of the research, and then the distribution and gathering of the data to determine results and draw conclusions. Breaking these down into further subcategories, is first to review the preparation stage.

Study Limitations

Study limitations within the research design would be the selection of the sample, as they would be confined to the college athletes within a certain region of California. Additionally, the technology and instruments by which the survey is collected may result in issues. These steps will take the raw data received from participants and transform it into meaningful insights that may confirm other research already surrounding this topic or bring an entirely new dimension to previous assertions made within the field. Finally, a projected limitation is within the survey's written nature. While time and review were given to the format and phrasing of the questions, there still is room for confusion or misinterpretation depending on the athlete with what their

answer should be. Therefore, misunderstanding of the question may result in a recorded answer that was not conducive of the athletes' actual answer towards that question. Clarifying the expected limitations of this study will give the hypotheses, the data, and the results, a more objective and fairer conclusion.

Importance and Implications of Research

Looking at the bigger picture, the results of this research could be beneficial to a variety of audiences. For coaches, it could better inform which motivations and encouragement would be beneficial within their leadership and coaching style. In contrast, it could provide motivating factors that could lead to negative mental health effects, such as stress, burnout, or increased self-criticism. Further, which factors could contribute to the athlete giving up on their sport or team? This research would aid in the awareness of athletes, if they are better able to contribute where their motivation comes from, they may be better able to understand and process how they perform on a given day, and what factors affect that. Especially in a team sport setting, where athletes depend on each other to achieve their goals and have fun, this information could help them better understand their teammates and why they do what they do. From a coaching perspective, family members of athletes can better understand how to support their loved one and their athletic journey. Also, from a marketing perspective, this information could better inform the marketing strategy of businesses whose target audiences are involved in the athletic community. The driving factor of marketing is to understand consumer's wants and needs so that the business knows how to curate a service or product for them. Therefore, by understanding their motivations, businesses can optimally suit their marketing strategy, and product or service development to optimize their offering for that athlete consumer.

METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

To achieve the aforementioned aims and objectives of the study, the data collection method for the research utilized one on one interviews with the selected athlete to collect quantitative and qualitative data to be reported in an anonymous fashion. The quantitative data was collected through a Qualtrics survey with ordinal, binary, nominal, and dichotomous variables (Appendix E). The Likert questions used to measure the level of extrinsic and intrinsic motivations within the athlete were inspired by the SMS-II (Appendix A). Some of the questions came from the scale, representing their appropriate motivation. This scale was used for its strength and validity at clarifying intrinsic and extrinsic motivations into potential touchpoints for the athlete.

Following suit to those who have used a revised version of the scale in later years for different studies, this research did the same with adjustment to meet the criteria for this research. The motivations as they related to the athlete's interaction with their sport were broken into two categories. One section of questions relates to the athletes during a game, and the other section investigates why they participate in their sport. Moving to the qualitative data, the insight was achieved through brief, one on one, conversation with the athlete. The structure of the interview was built around four predetermined questions as jumping off points. The combination of these data retrieval methods provides each a unique strength, to meet the research aims. The quantitative data gives the analysis of the sample's motivations clarity, focus and uniformity of response. Also, this allows the athlete's intended level of demographic and historical information to be known. Ultimately supplying a clear and appropriate framework for understanding the athlete's journey in their sport thus far, at present, and in the intended future. Having this portion of the responses achieved through a self-assessment survey platform gives the necessary privacy and timing for the athlete to comfortably complete the internal reflection process without having

to speak their responses aloud. Therefore, aiming to eliminate some of the bias present in self-assessments when there can be embarrassment or reservation in telling someone these perspectives. Because the responses from this portion can be measured by statistical means of comparison, leads to findings that have the potential to be more conclusive. Additionally, other studies conducted within this subject matter have successfully used quantitative data to answer their research questions. For example, the SMS-II was used in a survey of Lithuanian basketball players of various ages to see if emotional intelligence correlated with motivation (Sukys et al., 2019). Qualitative data is key to understanding the perspective and experience that would go further than a predetermined set of options to select from. This data was gathered in the form of oral, one on one interviews over zoom. The meetings were recorded with audio and fed through an AI (Artificial Intelligence) transcript generator for further analysis. Because this information would require a self-analysis on behalf of the athlete in the conversation, having targeted questions to give room for the athlete to explain themselves in a way that the prior Qualtrics survey does not provide is beneficial. Therefore, allowing space to have a picture created that is indicative of the athlete's psychological motivations by way of experience and perspective. Using this type of data alongside the quantitative data creates a clarified picture that properly encompasses each athlete's perspective on themselves, so that the sample size may be legitimately compared.

Survey Design

The questionnaire's design combined questions from the Sport Motivation scale (SMS), both revised and in their original form, and questions created specifically for this survey. The Sport Motivation scale, in its original and revised form, is well-respected and has been used in multiple studies pertaining to athletes and motivation. The Sport motivation scale is a useful tool for this subject matter when appropriately applied. That is, because the survey measures an additional

factor that is not being studied in this research, namely amotivation. Therefore, the focus will be to create a survey that integrates the portions of the SMS-II that are relevant to this topic, revised where appropriate to reflect the aims of this study specifically. Further, because the motivations pertaining to the study are differentiated by individual questions, questions were chosen or revised based on the measured motivation. Additionally, the survey will have questions that look at two different areas of the athlete's involvement with the sport. Though there are a variety of revised versions of the SMS scale present within the subject matter based on the year, this survey does not claim to hold the same analysis process as the original survey, as the survey is not used in its original totality, therefore cannot be treated in academic analysis the same way that the SMS scale would assert. Therefore, the analysis process given to this survey, in conjunction with the due works of Mallett et al, is unique to the question's correlated motivation as intended by the measured motivation. To assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire's nominal data, the Cronbach alpha test was conducted with the results and yielded a 0.60 rounded result (Appendix F). $0.5 < \alpha < 0.8$ is considered moderate (acceptable) reliability, therefore this was encouraging to move ahead with during analysis (Ekolu et al., 2019).

Intention of Questions

One area will be the motivational aspect as it pertains to performance. This will look like a set of clarified, close-ended questions that will address different potential factors, activities, or mindsets that lead up to their participation in the sport. The other area of interest will be the motivational aspect as it pertains to their commitment to the sport, whether that is past or future (looking ahead to if they seek to continue in the sports past college whether professionally or recreationally). Also, within the area of commitment to sport, questions would be asked that highlight how long they played in their sport prior to this season, and if they were involved with any other type of team sport prior to the type of sport they play now. This added dimension to

commitment to sport was to aid in the investigation of analyzing if there was a large turnover in the athletes who have been in their sport. Additionally, if there was any correlation between the amount of time given to the single sport correlating to how committed they are to continuing to participate in that type of team sport. Thirdly, questions that ask the participant for relevant demographic information. Those will be as follows: age, gender, and collegiate year the student is currently in.

Sample

The four college athletes in this case study were selected through the non-probability sampling method of convenience sampling to select athletes based on willingness to participate or coach recommendation. None of the participants had any prior association or relation with the principal investigator or the co-investigator. The only information known about the participants prior to the interview was their sport, grade level, and affiliated university. To properly address the athletes throughout the analysis process, each participant was assigned a correlating letter to categorize their responses.

Athlete A is a member of the women's basketball team at a public four-year university at the first-year level. Athlete B is a member of the women's volleyball team at a public four-year university at the junior level. Athlete C is a member of the men's baseball team at a four-year private university at the senior level. Athlete D is a member of the men's football team at a community college at the community college level.

Influence of Existing Research's Methodology

The methodology used by surrounding research that coincides, in part, with the research this thesis is involved with, aids in the foundation for the practice of this methodology. Therefore, helping to build the criteria for what this methodology looks like, as well as how it may improve

on the surrounding studies' self-admitted gaps in research procedure. Background questions that define the length of time an athlete had been involved in their corresponding team sport were used in a study looking at emotional intelligence and motivation within basketball players of Lithuania (Sukys et al., 2019). Although their research did not aim to review the correlations between motivation and the commitment of an athlete to their sport, they still included that question as a foundation for understanding the athletic background of the participant (Sukys et al., 2019). They too used the SMS-II, but used the scale in its completion, as this research team was not trying to look at any specific categories of motivations, but rather all types of motivations (Sukys et al., 2019). The unrevised version of the Sport Motivation Scale was used in research that investigated athletes' use of music before and after training and competitions within the participants at the 2017 Olympics of Mexico (Cocca et al., 2018). They used a combination of 2 standardized scales, SMS, and the Flow State Scale, in addition to a self-created questionnaire of music preferences and habits (Cocca et al., 2018). However, not all athletic studies exploring motivation as a factor in their research question used any version of the Sport Motivation Scale. A California State University, Fresno, study looked at the role of passion for the athlete's sport in college student-athlete's effort and motivations in both athletics and academics (Yukhymenko-Lescroart 2021). To find this, they used The Passion Scale and the Athletic and Academic Identity Scale that had already been established within the sport psychology field before conducting this study. That is, many studies have used a version of the Sport Motivation Scale, but not all. Others, such as research examining gender differences in levels of sport commitment and commitment determinants (functional and obligatory commitment) used no standardized scale at all, but rather created a solely self-made survey that was composed of concepts that had been validated (Wigglesworth et al., 2012).

FINDINGS

Background to Qualitative and Quantitative Data

The study's results are categorized in two ways, to enhance the insight available to this study.

The discussion begins by reviewing the individual athlete, using conceptualization based on a narrative analysis framework with qualitative data, and a summary of the findings pertaining to the quantitative data. Additionally, the results are reviewed collectively, in pursuit of building the basis for any overarching themes, and to answer the research questions. In doing so, the relevancies of this study can be appropriately examined alongside other research and theories surrounding the subject matter.

The ordinal data gathered from the Likert scale questions measures the weight of the external and internal motivations of the athlete by two categories of participation with the game. The difference is in the environment and purpose of the athlete's participation with the game. First, is how the athlete thrives during a game, and second, why they practice their sport overall. The motivations that drive an athlete in each aspect of their athletic journey can vary depending on the context by which they participate in their sport. Namely, the accolades, external stimuli, and purpose of the game, compared to the practice of the sport can result in different driving motivations. Additionally, the variation of the sport type in the context of this case study is notable, as all athletes are answering from the perspective of varying gameplay that is natural to team sports having inherent qualities that can differ.

Given the 7-point Likert scale options, if an athlete were to correlate completely to every question that measured either intrinsic or extrinsic motivation, then their ordinal score would total to 21 for that section, as they would be answering a 7 for all 3 questions that correlate to that questions' underlying motivation. Therefore, understanding the frequency and average of the

results pertaining to the athlete can help to uncover how these motivations compare to one another. These results will be viewed altogether, with all four athletes at the ending results section.

Athlete A

Athlete A is a member of the women's basketball team at a public four-year university. She is an 18-year-old female athlete, participating most recently in her sport at the freshman level. She has played basketball on a team for 10+ years, and has also been a part of baseball, softball, volleyball, and soccer at a team level. She plans to continue playing on her basketball team for the remainder of her college career, and while she plans to play basketball recreationally after college, she does not plan to pursue her sport professionally.

Reviewing the data for the motivation breakdown present in her relationship with basketball showed proclivity towards intrinsic motivation, as opposed to extrinsic. Specifically, in both the categories why she practiced basketball, and in the context of what she thrived off of during a game. Moreover, she was 85.71% (sum score of 18) intrinsically motivated compared to 71.43% (sum score of 15) extrinsically motivated during a game. For the investigation into why she practices basketball, he registered 76.19% (sum score of 16) intrinsically motivated, compared to 66.67% (sum score of 14) extrinsically motivated for practicing basketball.

Delving into the individual questions that showed consistencies will give a greater understanding into the reasoning of these sum scores. During a game, the leading motivations athlete A thrived most off was not letting her team down and the pleasure she feels from overcoming challenges and improving weak points. Receiving the score corresponding exactly to the prompt. Not letting

her team down correlates to introjected regulation, specifically the portion that aims to behave in such a way (or in the context of an athlete, perform) to avoid feelings of guilt or anxiety that can be associated with outcomes. And the pleasure she feels from overcoming challenges and improving weak points she feels relates to the intrinsic motivation towards knowledge. Whereas showing others how good she was at his sport had the least correspondence, with only 2 being selected on the scale. This also measures the extrinsic motivation form of introjected regulation, but unlike the behaviors towards avoiding guilt or anxiety, this question measures toward ego or pride. This highlights the importance of putting the question's underlying motivation into context, defining it as towards the measurement of motivation from fear or confidence. Closely, intrinsic motivation towards stimulation received a 6 out of 7, and the crowd feedback also received a 6 out of 7. The weight of the crowd feedback shows how receptive she is to her environment during a game, as she is taking in that portion of the external stimuli. When exploring why she practices her game, her rating indicated that doing so because she doesn't like to lose corresponds not exactly, but highly to her, as well as doing so because of the enjoyment with his teammates at a top score of 7. This highlights the presence and importance of competence and relatedness as described by the self-determination theory.

Moving into the interview with athlete A, the first question to start off was asking her about who has inspired her in her athletic journey thus far,

“Probably my parents, and then also my brother. I think I get more inspiration to play from my parents, but my brother more, inspired like the way that I play, I guess.”

This comment shows the presence of family in her journey as an athlete, both in the way she plays and why she plays. This signifies the ongoing weight of the support of her family, and in

the way she models her game, which has a deep integration with her own participation in the sport. The next question asked about her recommendation of the sport. She says,

“I would say yeah I’ve played like, a lot of sports and basketball is more like, upbeat kinda and I think that’s pretty interesting for like anybody. Anyone could watch a basketball game, but I can’t say the same for like baseball or softball. I played all different sports. I think that depending on my situation, like how old I was, that was my favorite one, the one that resonated with me changed, so I think towards the end when I was deciding what I wanna do for college is when basketball hit me the most. And then when I was a freshman in high school, but like when I was a junior, senior, I liked softball so it really just depends on timing I guess.”

She appeals to the accessibility and adrenaline of the game, in that the learning curve to basketball can hold differently in her opinion compared to baseball or softball. From this comment and information alone, it cannot be further elaborated how deep her commitment to her sport is communicated. However, her recommendation of the sport expresses her interest in believing it to be interesting for anyone. The last question asked referred to her favorite memory. Athlete A says,

“My favorite is probably in my senior, no sorry my freshman year of high school, we won, like the regional tournament, I guess, and that was something that hadn’t happened in 10 years and at that time I wasn’t super interested in basketball, and I think that kind of sparked more of an interest in me, and yeah.”

This memory showcases the weight of a win in high school that moved beyond predisposed odds. Specifically, in obtaining success that had not happened in years. This also reveals competence as related to the self-determination theory because her interest was sparked through a win that made her consider basketball more seriously. This extrinsic motivation of success as

determined by an outsider event can be a powerful catalyst to self-realization in competence that there is the ability to achieve what she is aiming for.

Athlete B

Athlete B is a member of the women's volleyball team at a public four-year university. She is a 21-year-old female athlete, participating most recently in her sport at the junior level. She has played volleyball on a team for 10+ years and has also been a part of soccer at the team level. She plans to continue playing on her volleyball team for the remainder of her college career. She does plan to pursue volleyball professionally after college, either in a coaching or player position. However, she does not plan to continue participating in her sport recreationally after college.

Overall, Athlete B was driven more intrinsically in both the context of the game and practice. That is, 76.19% intrinsically motivated (sum score of 16) compared to 76.19% extrinsically motivated during a game (sum score of 15). Similarly, 80.95% (sum score of 17) intrinsically motivated, compared to 66.67% (sum score of 14) extrinsically motivated for practicing volleyball. However, the margin between the extrinsic and intrinsic motivations during the game was slimmer than for practicing her sport.

A closer look at the trends with the individual question would show that during a game, athlete B's driving extrinsic motivation was the desire to not let her team down, making the selection of that sentiment corresponding exactly. Whereas the other two questions measuring external motivation both received a moderate score of 4 each. With the intrinsic motivation measurements, the questions measuring the themes of emotions felt during the game and personal improvement with the sport's gameplay were answered with a 6 and 7, respectively.

When looking into the extrinsic motivations for practicing her sport, the relationship of teammates came strongly again, with the enjoyment of the relationships with her teammates corresponding exactly to why she practices her sport. Similarly, the leading intrinsic motivation that also received a 7, to correspond exactly, was about the feeling she gets being totally immersed in playing a sport she likes, tying back to its inherent satisfaction by way of the feeling from it.

So what are some leading takeaways from this ordinal data for athlete B? The theme of relatedness, as expressed by the self-determination theory, is consistently prevalent in both contexts of the athlete's relation with the sport. The relationships with the teammates, whether by way of enjoyment, or in terms of introjected regulation to avoid guilt or anxiety through letting teammates down, is a notable presence in this athlete's time with the sport. Additionally, the intrinsic motivation towards accomplishment and stimulation as referred to by the SMS-II, are prevalent for athlete B in the respective context.

Moving towards the qualitative insight gained from the interview, it is interesting to see how the development of the athlete's journey is shaped by various influences and perspectives held by athlete B. When asked if there has been anyone that has inspired her in her athletic journey so far, whether it be a professional athlete, or someone she has known personally, athlete B said, *“Um, well, I actually started playing volleyball when I was only eight years old, seven, eight years old. And that started because my mom used to play and my grandfather decided to like, hold a couple like clinics and stuff. So that's how I became interested in the sport. And that's kind of always been like, a very, like, important thing to me. Like I've always worn until like, I came to Fullerton, I've always worn like, my mom's jersey number, and things like that. And then professionally, I've always looked up to a certain player. Her name is Morgan hence. And ever*

since I was younger, I'd go to her college games at Stanford. And now she plays professionally, I even got the chance to coach with her this past year, which was like an amazing thing. And so she's always been a huge inspiration to me."

Showing the influence of the connection back to her family in her athletic journey, with the significance of their relation to volleyball, and the sentimentality of keeping her mom's jersey number if she was able, furthers the psychological need for relatedness being strong.

Additionally, the connection of relationships and influence of others in the world of volleyball, is weaved into her position as a volleyball athlete. Further, the presence of Morgan Hence, as a professional athlete inspiration, is important to note in different facets. One, because she has been a consistent influence regardless of age, as athlete B cites how she has always looked up to her, even going to her games when she was younger. Further, athlete B will later explain her opportunity to work alongside Morgan Hence as an adult, and the impact that her coaching mindsets has had on her as a player. She could have also been a part of the top three reasons for starting her sport, as athlete B cited admiration of a professional athlete being a factor. Therefore, the professional athlete influence for Athlete B is unique in that it grew up with her and formed into a mentorship and partnership rather than merely third-party admiration. Authors Rusbult, Johnson, and Morrow, state that "commitment should be greater to the degree that the individual has invested numerous resources in the relationship either intrinsically (e.g., time, effort, self-disclosure) or extrinsically (e.g., mutual friends, shared memories, or material possession) (Rusbult et al., 1986). This is supported by the time and shared memories that Athlete B poured into her relation and admiration of Morgan Hence as she related to volleyball, positively affecting her commitment to volleyball. Especially with the emphasis on having that influence be present before, during, and after adolescence, as 70% of adolescents pursuing sports drop out by the age of 13 (Fraser-Thomas et al., 2016; Woods & Butler, 2021)" (Battaglia, et al., 2024).

When asked if there were any motivations or perspectives that she thought really helped her in her sport, athlete B said,

“Um, yeah, so my mom has always just been like, do it for yourself, like love the sport. And that's how I've kind of been self motivated in that way. She kind of taught me that it was never like that I'm doing it because she did it or that because my grandfather was also a coach, who was always just finding motivation within myself. And then with Morgan hence, I've always been motivated by just her drive, like, the position that she played in college wasn't in a position where she played her whole life. And that taught me to be flexible. And then she taught me some great softball when I was coaching with her as well. But like, the three important things like in sports, or like anything, is that we can always control our attitude. Our, sorry, our attitude, our communication, and our effort. And that's always been like a huge thing, Huge thing to me, because volleyball is just the game of like mistakes so that I know that mistakes are gonna happen. But there's things that I can control.”

What is important to see in this response is the level of autonomy that athlete B is regarding. The self-admitted presence of self-motivation, control over attitude, communication, and effort are all highly contributing to a sense of building autonomy in the athlete. Additionally, the citing of seeing what you can control, where there are bound to be mistakes, clarifies the presence of autonomy where competency can fail, especially in game play. The intrinsic motivations of doing something for the enjoyment of it, the love of the game, rather than the family influences is also showing how athlete B's relationships spurred her towards positive relation towards volleyball as a sport, and her mindsets as an athlete.

She shares her favorite memory of her time as a volleyball player with recalling,

“When I was 12 years old, I, we had like a great season. Specifically, we got to compete at junior nationals. And we finished in the top four, which was a huge accomplishment for us. And that was the one year that I actually started traveling and playing volleyball. Like I traveled all over the US and doing that was a huge thing for me. And it was really great for my family. And because my dad took time off of work and made every single game every single tournament no matter where it was. And then in this past year, I was playing in one of our college games, there was a group of like, younger kids that came to watch and that like, warmed my heart so much, because that used to be me in the stands, like so excited to see the players. They were just waving and like anytime you'd wave back at them, they were super excited. It was just like the cutest thing ever. And that was a super great memory.”

The success athlete B had experienced prior to the statistical turning point of the age 13 dropout rate shows how the facilitation of competency in an athlete at a young age, when fostered with relational memories is powerful. The way she cites the relationships that pertain to the memory, namely through the presence of her dad at all the games, no matter the traveled distance.

Additionally, she cites an adult memory, where she sees herself in the eyes of the young players looking at her now, the way she had once done. The difference of these enjoyed memories shows the growth of athlete B in her journey. On the one hand, she was an adolescent experiencing the success of their season and traveling, and spending that with her family, as a player. Then, as a college athlete, looking at who she once was, figuratively with fondness for the young and excited kids watching her. This contributes to the weight that external motivations have on the life of an athlete. Such as successes from a game, admiration from others (kids), and the relationships in family fostered by external factors and events. So, while athlete B may have resonated more intrinsically in terms of her current mindsets for game play and practicing

volleyball, the weight of extrinsic motivation in a young adolescent, and college athlete, are still dominant.

Finally, looking towards Athlete B's commitment to her sport with its relation to others, and extending her perspective on her career towards advice for others, she expressed this,

“Yeah, I definitely would. Like as a coach, I really take pride in teaching younger kids and passing on my own knowledge and life experiences and sharing that with them. And just there's just like, a lot of happiness that comes with the game and a lot of great relationships because it is a team sport.”

From this response, it is evident that athlete B's extension of her dedication to volleyball moves into her commitment to facilitate the sport positively in the lives of other athletes through coaching. Even with the commonality between her grandfather's instruction position, and now into hers. The theme of relationships surfaces again, displaying the presence of meaningful relationships and connections, that correspond to the weight of relatedness from the self-determination theory.

Athlete C

Athlete C is a member of the men's baseball team at a private four-year university. He is a 22-year-old male athlete, participating most recently in his sport at the senior level. He has played baseball on a team for 10+ years, and has also been a part of soccer, cross country, and basketball at a team level. He plans to continue playing on his baseball team for the remainder of his college career. He does plan to pursue baseball professionally after college, either in a coaching or player position. He also plans to continue his sport recreationally after college.

Looking at the quantitative data that measured the weight of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, athlete C was driven more intrinsically in practicing baseball, but in the game's context, slightly more motivated. That is, 52.34% (sum score of 11) extrinsically motivated compared to 47.62% (sum score of 10) intrinsically motivated during a game. For the prompt of why he practices baseball, he showed 76.19% (sum score of 16) intrinsically motivated, compared to 57.14% (sum score of 12) extrinsically motivated for practicing baseball.

Taking a further look at how the individual questions were answered would show that during a game, athlete C thrived most off not letting his team down, and the energy and emotions he feels from participating in the game, receiving both 6 out of 7 on the Likert scale. Whereas the crowd feedback during a game, and the feeling of satisfaction he gets knowing that playing the sport is good and important for him, does not correspond to him at all. This could be due to the nature of the crowd's participation with baseball compared to other sports, or evidence of athlete C's ability to tap into an encompassing level of focus and concentration referred to commonly as being in the zone. The attention and discipline associated with this are signposts of a mental game. Mike Edger writes, "Entering the zone requires total commitment to game plan and the process of winning...Mentally tough athletes are at an advantage because they have the ability to tap into the zone more consistently in competition" (Edger 2012). This signpost of mindset and perspective, particularly in the setting of the mental gameplay aspect of baseball, and the significance of competition are prevailing themes in athlete C's data. Additionally, the commitment taken towards the game play itself, regardless of external factors and stimuli, supports a self-sustained procedure to gameplay. This autonomy of controlling one's focus and behavior is positive towards the studied longevity of an athlete in their sport. Especially because of how athlete C rated himself in terms of the feeling of losing. That is, when exploring why he practices his game, the only response that he believed corresponded exactly to him, was doing so

because he did not like the feeling of losing. This aligns with the previous study that examined differences in exercise motivation between genders for college students, which concluded that men tended to be motivated by intrinsic factors such as competition and challenge (Gillison et al., 2009). Like the other athletes discussed thus far, enjoying relationships with his teammates and fellow athletes corresponded highly, getting ranked a 6.

So, what are some prevailing themes from athlete C's ordinal data? When considering the self-determination theory alongside these motivations, the weight of competency and relatedness emerges strong. When athlete C correlates the enjoyment of his teammates relationships and gaining mastery in his sport as to avoid the feeling of losing, there is compelling evidence for his motivations being shaped by these two psychological needs that the theory puts forth.

Additionally, with intrinsic motivation having the stronger pull when it came to why he practices baseball, compared to the other extrinsic factors. The feeling, or pursuit of, competence in athlete C is supported in the theme of relatedness, as expressed by the self-determination theory, is consistently prevalent in both contexts of the athlete's relation with the sport. The relationships with the teammates, whether by way of enjoyment, or in terms of introjected regulation to avoid guilt or anxiety through letting teammates down, is a notable presence in this athlete's time with the sport. Additionally, the intrinsic motivation towards accomplishment and stimulation as referred to by the SMS-II, are prevalent for athlete B in the respective context (Appendix 3).

Moving towards the interview portion with athlete C, it is interesting to see how his responses and perspectives grew alongside his sum scale answers from the survey. When asked if there has been anyone that has inspired him in his athletic journey so far, whether it be a professional athlete, or someone he has known personally, athlete C explains,

“Yeah, I mean, I don't know if you want me to drop like a list of names. There's definitely a lot of people growing up from Seattle. So it was Felix Hernandez and Ichiro, were the big Mariner stars at the time. So I definitely wanted to emulate them and be like them. And then the other for me was Kobe Bryant. Growing up I was a big basketball fan. I'm not a Lakers fan anymore. I'm a Sixers fan. But he was definitely like the basketball player I wanted to be like, and definitely take some aspects of like, his mentality and his approach to the game. So I would say those three probably stand out above the rest. With Kobe Bryan, obviously pretty famous for his whole like the mamba mentality thing. So I definitely took some aspects from that. Insofar as the other two I mentioned, I was just growing up watching them play on my favorite team, and they were really good. So I was like, I want to be like those guys. Cuz I don't like doing things partway. If I'm going to do something, I want to be really good at it. And so I definitely wanted to be like them in that regard”

Athlete C's response shows the different avenues his inspirations have led into and how they informed his role as an athlete at different ages. The concept of proximity and team loyalty is prevalent in the way that the Mariners were close in relation to where he grew up, in Seattle. He mentions how he wanted to emulate their game, be like them. Specifically, he regards how if he is going to do something, he wants to be good at it and not do it part way. This aligns back to the emphasis that competency has on athlete C's athletic journey. This corresponds with his response to not liking the feeling of losing. Showing a strong drive towards competency in his pursuit through the game. Additionally, it is interesting to see how the mindsets and perspectives of professional athletes outside of his existing sport play a role notable enough in his adolescence to remember even now. Throughout his sports history, basketball was a sport he had been a part of, so the prospect of looking to professional athletes in this sport would make sense.

Personal family influences with the connection of baseball did not have a prevailing effect on athlete C, as he says,

“Not baseball. My mom swam in college. And my dad actually did equestrian, which is kind of an interesting one. But yeah, they were both very athletic. They never pushed me into doing sports. But once I became interested in baseball, they definitely helped me kind of along the path, and were able to give me advice and tips from their careers”

This shows that the motivation that could be gathered from his family extended into how he moved along in his journey, rather than in the purpose or origination of baseball in the first place. Signaling more autonomy, and intrinsic motivation, as the inherent fulfillment and enjoyment of the game were leading beyond the external influence of being pushed into sports through the lens of a generational commitment and responsibility, rather than an intrinsic one.

When talking about his favorite memory about his time as an athlete, he also recounted a win from earlier in his life, specifically high school.

“So my junior year, we won the state championship in high school and my brother was on that team. He's two years younger than me. So he's a freshman. He didn't really play, but he was on the team with me. Being able to share that with him through the sport was awesome. You know, when I got to high school, we weren't very good. So to kind of see all our hard work pay off a couple years later, and to be able to share that with friends. And you know, share it with family members really close to me was pretty special.”

The aspects of sharing the sport with his brother, sharing the win with his friends, and seeing the improvement of his team turn into successes that translated into a state championship are all

ingredients for a very memorable time. Seeing the role of success, combined with relationships that enhance the memory of it, is understandably a landmark in the journey of an athlete.

Because they are not only seeing the fruition of failure, doubt, and hard work, but sharing those emotions with those closest to them for that victory to be obtained. Having tangible experiences of seeing hard work pay off early in the journey of the athlete, especially in team sports. It is said that team sports are associated with improved health outcomes because of the built in social aspect that comes with the participation in the sport, compared to individual activities (Eime et al., 2013).

To add a final level of inquiry into athlete C's commitment to his sport, the question was asked if he would recommend his sport for another to play. His response was,

“Man, I would say don't play if you can't handle failure. The thing my coaches at every level have always liked to say is baseball is a game of failure. Even like the best hitters in the major leagues fail seven out of 10 times. And so from a young age, you kind of learn how to deal with not being successful. Which I think is a pretty valuable skill because you know, not everything's always going to be, you know, sunshine and roses. So I think that's good. And then the, just the team building aspect, you're spending a lot of time with people, and you're working together with them on the field. And I think you can build really valuable relationships through the sport. So, from that aspect of it, I would definitely recommend it. But I think that it's not something that you should do if you're not comfortable with struggling and having to go through some difficult stuff.”

His response illuminates both the value in the team sport aspect, and the conditional nature around the pursuit towards the type of sport. By prefacing the journey with baseball to be marked by failure, there is an understanding of the need for competence that can be infringed on in athletics, due to team sports having a large amount of structure out of one's control. Athlete C had already demonstrated in different facets how avoiding the feeling of loss was a driving factor for him, so to admit that baseball is a game of failure is likely to allude to the amount of failure he has felt in the game. Therefore, he is demonstrating commitment to baseball in this comment by not only understanding how there is failure up into the professional level but by seeing how he does not enjoy that aspect of loss yet continues with the sport anyway. Additionally, providing that mindset into how you would recommend the sport to others displays a level of agreement with the actuality of how the game play is going to go, whether it is easily dealt with or not. Further, the impact that the coaches have by telling him, at diverse levels of baseball, that failure is a part of it, even going as far as to provide a statistic to display that from a professional league standpoint. This shows the importance of good coaches that are consistent to build competence in athletes at all touchpoints in their growth in the sport.

Athlete C explained what he believed to be unique to the gameplay of baseball by saying,

“Um, I mean, I think there's definitely a huge mental aspect that goes into baseball that I think is beyond a lot of other sports. In baseball, there's so much time in between plays. I think golf is probably the only other sport that's similar in this regard, where you just have so much time to think about it. I think it was Yogi Berra that said baseball is 90% mental, and the other half is physical, which I think sums it up pretty well. There's just so much thinking. And there's so much like, strategy, that goes on in the game. My coach likes to call it the game within the game. Like you're almost fighting yourself sometimes when you're out there. Because when things aren't

going well, you'd have all this time to think about everything that's not going your way. And it can spiral really easily. And I think that just the very nature of baseball, where you have all this time in between pitches before the ball is put in play, kind of brings the mental aspects to the forefront. I've played every single position on the field at various points in my career, you know, in Little League, everyone kind of wants to be the star. So they want to be the shortstop, everyone wants to play shortstop. But then as you kind of grow up, you start to feel comfortable in different spots. Um, for me, I like being a pitcher because the game kind of revolves around you. So that the game can't start until you deliver the pitch. And that's, that's always kind of stood out to me is like, the pitcher is kind of at the center of it all. So it definitely, it can be difficult, I guess, when you're you're not doing well, because it's like, damn, Everyone's looking at me. But at the same time, it also kind of gives you a modicum of control over the rest of the game. And I appreciate that aspect.

Looking at this response, the idea of baseball having a heavy mental aspect as opposed to physicality during game play, makes motivations and mindsets all the more vital to the outcome of the play. This ties back to athlete C relating to the crowd feedback not having any impact on him thriving in the game, further associating that athlete C, in his position as pitcher, is focused on the game that he is playing in his head before that translates to the plays he makes with his pitch. This means that longevity in his career would need to include safeguards and boundaries to ensure that his mental game would not deteriorate due to its large translation into tangible game play. He mentions that he enjoys the game play, specifically the start of it, revolving around him with the role of pitcher. It is interesting to note when he cites that it can be difficult when it is not going well because everyone is looking at him, implying an invoking of guilt or anxiety. This correlates to introjected regulation, a form of extrinsic motivation that is tied to behaviors that

aim to avoid guilt, anxiety, and shame. Or, to improve the ego, feelings of value, or pride. A study showed that in boys, “introjected regulation was largely related to social factors, such as avoiding social disapproval and attaining ego enhancement” (Gillison et al., 2009). This same level of introjected regulation shows up in his ordinal data, with both questions measuring introjected regulation corresponding moderately at a 4. Therefore, extrinsic motivation is still a notable part of athlete C’s game play, and in the view of himself in relation to baseball.

Athlete D

Athlete D is a member of the men’s football team at a public two-year university. He is a 24-year-old male athlete, participating most recently in his sport at the sophomore level. He does not plan to continue playing on a football team for the remainder of his college career. He does plan to pursue football professionally after college, either in a coaching or player position. He also plans to continue his sport recreationally after college.

Athlete D measured the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations present in his relationship with football and showed preference towards intrinsic motivation, not extrinsic. In both why he practiced football and in the context of what he thrived off during a game, as the question prompts stated. Specifically, 80.95% (sum score of 17) intrinsically motivated compared to 42.86% (sum score of 9) intrinsically motivated during a game. For the investigation into why he practices football, he registered 80.95% (sum score of 17) intrinsically motivated again, compared to 71.43% (sum score of 15) extrinsically motivated for practicing football.

Going further into the individual questions that showed patterns or correlation will give a greater understanding into the makeup of these sum scores. During a game, the leading motivation

athlete C thrived most off was not letting his team down and the energy and emotions he feels from participating, receiving the score of corresponding exactly to the prompt. Not letting his team down correlates to introjected regulation, specifically the portion that aims to behave in such a way (or in the context of an athlete, perform) to avoid guilt or anxiety. And the energy and emotions he feels from the game relate to the intrinsic motivation towards stimulation.

Whereas showing others how good he was at his sport had the least correspondence, with only a score of 2 being selected on the scale. This too measures the extrinsic motivation form of introjected regulation, but unlike the behaviors towards avoiding guilt or anxiety, this question measures toward ego or pride. This categorizes the importance of not only understanding the underlying motivation measured, but its context towards what the motivation is coming from, fear or confidence. When exploring why he practices his game, his rating indicated that doing so because he does not like to lose corresponds exactly to him, as well as doing so because of the enjoyment with his teammates. This responds once again, as with baseball player, athlete C, to the presence and importance of competence and relatedness as described by the self-determination theory. They have the ability to work together because the aim to not let his teammates down as an individual in the game, and not letting the entire team down by a collective loss of a game, go hand in hand. Additionally, if practicing your sport, and putting in the arduous work towards strategy and refinement of plays leads towards a decrease in the chance of personal fault, and therefore translating into letting the team down, there is harmony. That is, in that these motivations are working to support one another in the athlete's mental game.

Moving towards the qualitative data of this analysis, the conversation with athlete D began in understanding who has inspired him in his athletic journey. He responded with,

“Um, I think it's changed a lot. From when I was younger, when I was younger, I really looked at Kobe Bryant and his mentality and like, the way he looks at everything. And then the older I've gotten, the more it's changed to still having that mentality, uh then you look at different athletes, like someone I like to uh think about is John Jones. He struggles with like anxiety and stuff like that. And so he has a lot of really good quotes on that, that helps me because I struggle with anxiety. And so he's somebody that I looked up to Conor McGregor, couple fighters, and then once you start getting into like, like football players, it'd be like Jason Kelce, Travis Kelce. Because of like, their upbringing, because they're from Ohio, and then I'm from Indiana, so we kind of, not the exact same upbringing, but it's kind of like, it's almost like, not identical, but like, you can kind of see similarities. And so those people yeah.”

The role of professional athletes makes a return in this case again, in two ways. One in the relation to the athletes in terms of their background rather than their relation to the game. For example, with the Kelce brothers, the Midwest commonality. As well as with John Jones, and his relationship with their commonality in mental health and the professional athlete being able to speak to that. From this dialogue, it can be seen how the role of the professional athlete in the inspiration of his journey does not look like in terms of gameplay, position on the field, or necessarily mindset in the game (although anxiety can certainly come into consideration during game play). Instead, it looks like seeing the relation between himself as an individual in background and personality, with that of these professional athletes. Additionally, he notes how these influences have changed over time, indicative of how role models change and morph as athletes themselves do.

Regarding the aspect of family influence with his journey as an athlete, the following was said,

“I'd like to think that I came up on it on my own, but I've been playing football since I was in first grade. Like started in flag and then we've always like, holidays like, family holidays and stuff. We've always played football and basketball and this and that. So there's definitely family influences in it. But I... I fell in love with it and like, kept doing it on my own kind of thing. No, I didn't keep playing because of anybody, but I fell in love with it because of somebody. Like my mom, she, I don't think she cared if I was in football because there was times when I was like, I don't know if I want to play football anymore. Or I don't know. And she was like, I don't care what you do. But I just want you to be happy kind of thing. And then with my dad, it's been a little bit different. He's more like, I want you to play something like I want you to play football, like whatever you play, you're gonna be good at but like, I want you to play something like, and football and basketball are like his biggest ones. Kind of thing. So yeah.”

This response sheds light on the origination of the sport's interest being external to the athlete, specifically in relation to family influence and memories from childhood. But the differentiation between the exposure to the sport, and the continuation of it, is drawn clearly. This shows autonomy over the pursuit of the sport because it allows self-regulation and inherent fulfillment for the sport's love that is not contingent on others' approval or denial of it for the athlete. This is a positive internal form of motivation that leads to long term commitment to the context by which they participate in their sport.

When asked about his favorite memory, athlete D stated,

“There's so many that are coming to mind. So there was one time in my senior year of high school. I don't know why, but I'll always remember this. We played a team earlier in the season, and they beat us really bad. And then we played them in the playoffs, and we end up winning the

game by three. We picked the ball, like we had an interception in the end zone to win the game. And we're running down the sideline just like screaming my head off. And me and my best friend like even to this day, like there's a picture of it, were I like jump into his arms and like my hands are in the air. That's just one of those things I like it I always take with me is one of my favorite memories of just running down that sideline. And then we're running it when I'm running down the sideline. Like the team's like storming the field, the crowds going crazy. It just was like a really big moment. Yeah."

This memory cites the weight of a winning game, characterized by an underdog comeback context, paired with adrenaline and joy in the relationships between the team. Also, since it was unexpected in the context of an interception in the end zone to gain the victory, and the stimulation described in the painting of the environment, it is seen how this would be a standout experience. Additionally, this occurred in high school, which aligns with the other athletes' standout memories occurring from middle school or high school during formative years. Having notable memories present in the formative years of an athlete's journey that stir up competence and relatedness spurs forward an athlete to consider their long-term commitment to their sport.

Finally, when asked if he would recommend his sport to anyone, at any age, who hasn't played football, he says,

"So if it's like a middle schooler, I'd be like, yes, you should try it. It's a different kind of team building. And they're still in that development stage where they're going to teach you how to do everything properly, and they're going to teach you how to tackle, we're going to teach you how to hit. somebody that's like my age that hasn't played, then probably like, maybe go with flag

football, like, don't put pads on and go out there. Maybe start with like flag football or start with like, summer workouts and start learning things. (My college) does really well with allowing everyone whoever wants to come out, come out and then teaching them things. So I think that's how I would respond... football, it's so...it's a very long game, and then the sudden burst of contact plus speed, like physicality, all of it put together like I don't know, it's so shocking, because the one thing that pops in my mind, there's a picture of a kicker and a middle linebacker put together and it's like, how do these two people play this sport, but it's such a broad sport, that it kind of is almost all inclusive, too. Big guys. Little guys, fast guy slow, guys. Like it's one of those kinds of things.”

This response places the contingency to the recommendation on the age, and the type of football played, with the commitment to be able to learn and take direction. Interestingly enough, he cites the sport's large physicality aspect, with the simultaneous presence of positions built for many types of athletes in terms of build. This shows his commitment to his sport in terms of passing it along because there is thought behind the way, when, and how. That is, that the sport may not be a one size fits all in terms of where you are at in your life stage, but it has the space for many kinds of athletes to have their chance at the field.

Additionally, another thing to cite about the perceived commitment to his sport post his sophomore season shows a unique perspective compared to the other case study participants. That is, he continues to pursue football in a professional setting, whether in a player or coaching position, but not for the remainder of his college career. Studies would say that a lack of relatedness, autonomy, or competence could be a factor in this, however his results show a keen kinship to his teammates and to the adrenaline and challenge of the game. Therefore, this

direction of commitment could not be considered without further stated comments or data on athlete D's part. However, this is not in abandonment of football, as the recreational and professional intention to continue in the sport is made known.

Across Cases Results

After looking at each of these athletes individually, this portion of the results discusses overall commonalities in the findings, and the convergence or divergence of underlying motivations.

Breadth of Their Athletic Experience

All athletes had played their sport on a team level for 10+ years, and all athletes had played at least one other sport besides the team they were currently on. This shows the importance of pursuing non specialization of a sport at an early age, as research shows how this depletes the potential for longevity in an athlete's career contributes to a variety of factors

The Weight of the Winning Game

Every athlete cited their favorite memory surrounding their time as an athlete back to winning a game significant to them, from either middle school or high school, no matter their college grade level. Two of the four athletes discussed the enjoyment of these wins as they related to the unlikelihood of the win, and three of the four athletes cited the association with sharing that win with people closest to them. Since The level of competence that this gives adolescents

Motivations for Starting Sport

As shown in the Venn diagram below (Appendix B), of the 8 options to choose from for their top 3 motivations for starting their sport, the athletes had a lot of overlap. Namely, in the relational,

human influences that came from either family, friends, or admiration of a professional athlete in their sport.

Gender Differences

Some of the differences between athletes A and B, and C and D are as follows. The female athletes both rated themselves as not enjoying the feeling of competition, at a rating of 6, but the male athletes rated themselves highest at 7, saying that this corresponded to them exactly. Egli, Bland, Melton and Czech had investigated the differences in exercise motivation, between different college students based on gender, and results showed that men tended to be motivated by intrinsic factors such as competition and challenge more so than women (citing that women tended to be motivated by extrinsic factors such as weight management and appearance) (Larsen et al., 2021). Additionally, the female athletes both had little to no correlation to the sentiment that they would feel guilty, or lacking value, if they did not practice their sport. However, the

male athletes rated themselves either moderate, or slightly above moderately corresponding to that sentiment. The female athletes recommended their respective sports for others to play without exceptions, but the male athletes recommended their sport under certain conditions.

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations

The graphs below (Appendix C and D) show the trends between questions and athletes, highlighting overlap and prevailing differences.

Factors Found Supporting Long Term Commitment

In conclusion, a variety of insights can be gathered based on the individuals, their ambitions with their sport alongside their experience with the sport. One article from the *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* cited that an athlete’s enjoyment implicit beliefs in their ability, and family or social support, are factors that determine the intention to continue

practicing sport, and should be considered in future studies (Almagro et al., 2020) which is what this case study sought to look into alongside categories of motivations.

To summarize, for athletes B, C, and D, the heavy presence of intrinsic motivation, high senses of autonomy, self-regulation, and relatedness are all positive influences towards long term commitment to the sport. Studies show that, “Dropout players perceived themselves as significantly less competent, less autonomous, less related to their team, lower progress and less supported by their coach than persistent players” (Back et al., 2022). As seen in a variety of ways, the positive influence of coaches in advice, playmaking, and presence in the athlete moves against the notion of less support. Competence and autonomy showed prevalence in the athlete's life too, as discussed in the prior pages of the study. Relatedness was shown to be highly regarded in terms of teammates in the quantitative information, and in the varying roles of family in the qualitative data. Additionally, autonomy is supported through study results indicating that “when athletes feel that their coaches give them greater freedom in making decisions, give them alternatives, support them in their decisions, and ask for their input about the activities or exercises to be done in training, logically, it is likely that these athletes feel that they influence their own actions and, therefore, their perception of autonomy is positively affected” (Almagro et al., 2010). The fact that these three athletes played various positions in their sport, and athlete D cited the presence of coaches and friends giving advice on what positions would be best relative to the person, shows satisfaction in this area. Intrinsic motivation is essential to the long-term commitment of an athlete, specifically in that it is more enduring and substantial in spurring an athlete forward than extrinsic motivation. One study's author wrote, “some studies affirm that the intrinsic motivation [62] or autonomous motivation [14] of athletes must be increased to achieve success in sport. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation in young athletes is a predictor of their adherence to sports practice” (Almagro et al., 2020).

Other factors include the athlete's thoughtful recommendation of the sport, with professional athlete influences, and diversification of sport practice at an early age, are all impactful in predicting and correlating the length of the athlete's journey to their sport as opposed to dropping out of the sport. There is a lot of trending research coming out about the professionalization of youth sports, and the emphasis on sport specialization to create a professional athlete and prodigy out of a gifted adolescent athlete. Sport specialization is defined as, "year-round [8+ months per year] intensive training in a single sport at the exclusion of other sports," (McLellan et al., 2022). However, sport specialization has been studied to have negative effects on the health of an athlete, and their long-term commitment to the sport. Specifically, a systematic review shows how early sports specialization is not correlating to professional athletic success, but that late adolescent (compared with childhood) specialization, and broader training in childhood are linked to higher achievement (McLellan et al., 2022). Further, this systematic review regards this negatively to the length of their career with saying, "Studies have found early specialization to be detrimental to elite athlete success due to effects on injury and career length" (McLellan et al., 2022). However, all athletes had sports they had participated in outside their team now, signaling a lack of sport specialization as commonly defined.

For athlete A, her commitment to her sport extends only through college, and while the reasoning for that cannot be stated or conceptualized without further information, possibilities could include a stated late interest in pursuing basketball in college, as opposed to softball being her favorite sport her junior and senior year of high school, Additionally, that her love for the sport is not dampened by her career aspirations, but do not have a current place in that roadmap. The options for these decisions are endless, and therefore are taken out of review alongside the other athletes due to that desired difference in trajectory.

CONCLUSION

This case study opens the opportunity for further analysis to be done on a larger scale, with different questions and participants of different sports to see where the insights converge or diverge from the results of this study. Additionally, bringing in factors of performance, sport variation, and college level classification could bring about greater patterns to motivations within athletes. Limitations to this study are inherent to the size of the sample, and the potential for greater depth to be gained from the data format, so strengthening this process to be more inclusive in size and information gathered would benefit a future study. Overall, the takeaways of seeing the life of an athlete illuminated through touchpoints of relationships and mindsets of varying motivations can guide stakeholders of an athlete into doing their part to aid the athlete in having a healthy and enjoyable relationship with their sport.

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Appendix A

Scale Description

This scale assesses people's motivation for engaging in sport's activities. It assesses 7 types of motivation : intrinsic motivation toward knowledge, accomplishment and stimulation, as well as external, introjected and identified regulations, and amotivation. It contains 28 items (4 items for each of the 7 sub-scales) assessed on a 7-point scale.

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THE SPORT MOTIVATION SCALE (SMS-28)

*Luc G. Pelletier, Michelle Fortier, Robert J. Vallerand, Nathalie M. Brière, Kim M. Tuson and Marc R. Blais, 1995
Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology, 17, 35-53*

WHY DO YOU PRACTICE YOUR SPORT ?

Using the scale below, please indicate to what extent each of the following items corresponds to one of the reasons for which you are presently practicing your sport.

Does not correspond at all	Corresponds a little	Corresponds moderately	Corresponds a lot	Corresponds exactly
1	2	3	4	5

WHY DO YOU PRACTICE YOUR SPORT ?

- | | | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. For the pleasure I feel in living exciting experiences. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 2. For the pleasure it gives me to know more about the sport that I practice. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 3. I used to have good reasons for doing sport, but now I am asking myself if I should continue doing it. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 4. For the pleasure of discovering new training techniques. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 5. I don't know anymore; I have the impression of being incapable of succeeding in this sport. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 6. Because it allows me to be well regarded by people that I know. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 7. Because, in my opinion, it is one of the best ways to meet people. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 8. Because I feel a lot of personal satisfaction while mastering certain difficult training techniques. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 9. Because it is absolutely necessary to do sports if one wants to be in shape. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 10. For the prestige of being an athlete. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 11. Because it is one of the best ways I have chosen to develop other aspects of myself. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 12. For the pleasure I feel while improving some of my weak points. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 13. For the excitement I feel when I am really involved in the activity. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 14. Because I must do sports to feel good myself. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |

- | | | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 15. For the satisfaction I experience while I am perfecting my abilities. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 16. Because people around me think it is important to be in shape. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 17. Because it is a good way to learn lots of things which could be useful to me in other areas of my life. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 18. For the intense emotions I feel doing a sport that I like. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 19. It is not clear to me anymore; I don't really think my place is in sport. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 20. For the pleasure that I feel while executing certain difficult movements. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 21. Because I would feel bad if I was not taking time to do it. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 22. To show others how good I am good at my sport. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 23. For the pleasure that I feel while learning training techniques that I have never tried before. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 24. Because it is one of the best ways to maintain good relationships with my friends. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 25. Because I like the feeling of being totally immersed in the activity. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 26. Because I must do sports regularly. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 27. For the pleasure of discovering new performance strategies. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 28. I often ask myself; I can't seem to achieve the goals that I set for myself. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |

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KEY FOR SMS-28

- # 2, 4, 23, 27 Intrinsic motivation - to know
- # 8, 12, 15, 20 Intrinsic motivation - to accomplish
- # 1, 13, 18, 25 Intrinsic motivation - to experience stimulation
- # 7, 11, 17, 24 Extrinsic motivation - identified
- # 9, 14, 21, 26 Extrinsic motivation - introjected
- # 6, 10, 16, 22 Extrinsic motivation - external regulation
- # 3, 5, 19, 28 Amotivation

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Note: To use this scale you require only to mention the complete reference data.

Thank you for your interest.

Good luck in your research.

Appendix B

Appendix C

Appendix D

Appendix E

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON
ATHLETE SURVEY 2024

Using the scale below, please circle the number that indicates the extent to which each of the following items corresponds to the feelings or mindsets you have during a game.

Does not correspond at all	Corresponds a little	Corresponds moderately	Corresponds a lot	Corresponds Exactly		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

During A Game I Thrive Off Of:

1. The crowd feedback (cheers, applause, chants).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2. The pleasure I feel from improving my weak points and overcoming challenges.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3. The desire to not let my team down.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4. Showing others how good I am at my sport.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5. The energy and emotions I feel from participating in the game.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6. The feeling of satisfaction I get from knowing that playing the sport is good and important for me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Using the scale below, please circle the number that indicates the extent to which each of the following items corresponds to one of the reasons you are currently practicing your sport.

Does not correspond at all	Corresponds a little	Corresponds moderately	Corresponds a lot	Corresponds Exactly
1	2	3	4	5

I practice my sport because:

- | | | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 7. I enjoy the relationships with my fellow teammates and athletes. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 8. I don't like the feeling of losing. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 9. Because it allows me to be well regarded by people I know. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 10. Because I like the feeling I get when I am totally immersed in playing a sport that I like. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 11. For the pleasure of discovering new performance strategies. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| 12. Because I would feel guilty, or lacking value if I did not. | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |

13. Which of the following motivated you to start playing your sport? Select your **top 3** reasons from the list below.

- Family Influences
- Personal interest in the sport
- Scholarships/Financial Aid
- Exercise/health reasons
- The title and prestige of being known as an athlete
- Friend Influences

- Admiration of a professional athlete from the sport
 - Physical education school requirements
 - None of the above
-

Directions: Please indicate your answer to the following questions by circling "Yes" or "No" or checking the applicable boxes.

14. How long have you been playing your sport on a team? (At any level)

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-9 years
- 10 + years

15. Have you ever been a part of a sports team other than the sport team you are currently on?

If yes, which sport(s)?

Yes No

List other sport(s): _____

16. Do you plan to continue playing on your sports team for the remainder of your college career?

Yes No

17. Do you plan to continue with your sport professionally after college? (Whether on a team or in a coaching position)

Yes No

18. Do you plan to continue with your sport recreationally after college?

Yes No

19. Age: _____

20. What is your class level?

- Freshmen
- Sophomore
- Junior
- Senior

21. Gender: _____

Thank you for your feedback and participation in this survey.

